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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
**ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE
EVALUATION**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At any stage of the project.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>High, advanced quantitative and IT skills needed.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the project size and data volume.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>PC and software access, data collection costs if not available.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 34, 36, 37.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

The economic tools are used to:

- Assess the economic performance of the projects
- Monitor expenditure of the project
- Attract potential innovation investors.

Background and Logic

The evaluation of economic aspects of the project implementation has a special place in the donor agendas. Many programmes, especially those administered by the European Union, focus on spending funds allocated to achieving different objectives and priorities. There is a great interest in various economic aspects of the programmes' performance, which can be measured in many ways. Economic indicators are commonly acknowledged in the business practice and thus sought after by potential investors interested in the exploitation of the innovation projects' results. Some of the most popular approaches include:

Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)

This is a systematic approach focusing on the estimation of the strengths and weaknesses of alternatives to enable most benefits from the investments. It consists of determined options, which provide the best approach to achieving benefits while preserving savings. A step-by-step approach and mathematical formula are used to assess CBA, which can be also modified in a given project context. Computations involve discount rate and sensitivity analysis, among others. For whom would this approach be helpful and suitable? Which questions would a user ask when using this CBA?

Return on Investment (ROI)

This is a popular and rather simple performance metric applied for evaluation of the efficiency of an investment. Comparing the efficiency of a number of different investments can be also enabled with a dedicated formula. The calculation of ROI involves dividing the benefit (or return) of an investment by the cost of the investment. The ratio or percentage are used to describe the result.

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA)

This approach compares relative costs and outcomes (effects) of different courses of action. Unlike the CBA, in this method monetization is not necessary, thus it can be useful for evaluations in the public goods domains. CEA is most suitable, where cost-benefit analysis is constrained by the difficulty to estimate monetary value of benefits. Moreover, if incommensurability of assessed alternatives occurs, computations of ratio can be used. This method is particularly useful for the social and environmental outputs of a project because they can be ranked. Cost-Utility Analysis (CUA): this approach examines the preference of individuals in the context of multiple choices (different projects and interventions in the same area). Computations typically focus on the various cost types, e.g., personnel, facilities, equipment. The ingredients of a project need to be clearly distinguished as well as causality in the intervention logic.

Social Return on Investment (SROI)

Social, environmental, economic and other values are systematically incorporated into decision-making processes. SROI can be used for designing a Theory of Change or Business Plan. It is also applicable for assessing to what extent the impacts are realized or changes need to occur within the intervention logic. SROI is particularly useful for measuring non-monetary effects from the investment. Actors' perspectives are strongly encouraged as a way to determine the success/failure of the interventions. The approach often combines quantitative and participatory approaches to evaluation

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)

1. Identify costs of the investment / project
2. Assign monetary values to the investment (e.g. human resources, training)
3. Assign monetary value to the benefits (positive results of the project)
4. Compare costs and benefits using common metric
5. Calculate discount rate, net present value and sensitivity
 - » **Net Present Value (NPV)** = Σ Present Value of Future Benefits – Σ Present Value of Future Costs
 - » **Benefit-Cost Ratio** = Σ Present Value of Future Benefits / Σ Present Value of Future Costs

NPV = value / (1 + r)^t

“r” is the discount rate such as the rate of inflation

“t” is the service life of the project, that is, the period the project will provide benefits (e.g., year)

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA)

1. Express costs in a common monetary value (££) and the effectiveness of an option in terms of physical units
2. Because the two are incommensurable, they cannot be added or subtracted to obtain a single criterion measure
3. Compute the ratio of costs to effectiveness in the following ways:
 - CE ratio = C1/E1**
 - EC ratio = E1/C1**
 - where:
 - C1 = the cost of option 1 (in £)
 - E1 = the effectiveness of option 1 (in physical units)

Cost-Utility Analysis (CUA)

In order to assess the attribute utility you can do the following:

1. Proportional scoring: Use a common scale (eg. x/y axes) to assess
2. Direct method: Low or high value can be assessed on a numerical scale (eg. 0 for low and 100 for high)
3. Variable probability method: Stakeholders assess their preferences for varying amounts of a range of probabilities

Then assess the importance of weights:

1. Direct method: Individuals allocate a total (e.g. 100) of points among attributes according to their relative importance
2. Variable probability method: Individuals choose between two options when there is a 100% chance of A occurring and a 0% chance of B occurring; the probabilities are changed until there is no difference between whether they choose option A or B.

Return on Investment (ROI)

Option 1: ROI = (Net return on investment / Cost of investment) x 100%.

Option 1: ROI = (Final value of investment – Initial value of investment) / (Cost of investment) x 100%.

Social Return on Investment (SROI)

Establishing SROI is a rather complex task and often involves participatory process and data collection. The stages of SROI process can be grouped as follows:

1. Identification of the scope for the analysis
2. Identification of the relevant stakeholders
3. Mapping of the project outcomes
4. Providing evidence for the outcomes and assigning their values
5. Establishing the impact: (a) financial value of the investment and (b) value of social costs and benefits, supported with the calculations of the net present value and sensitivity analysis.

